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Diversification Of Economy And Its' Effect On Economic Growth In Karim Lamido Local Government Area, Taraba State, Nigeria

¹Nweze, Maria Ukamaka, MSc & ²Samuel Hyaluwa

Department Of Economics,
Federal University Wukari, Taraba State, Nigeria
¹amylast07@gmail.com/08067037743, 09160634733
²samuelcurtis87@gmail.com/08141274603

ABSTRACT

The major cause of decline in economic growth of any nation or region is lack of diversification of economy. This is because lack of diversification is believed to be detrimental to economic growth. This study investigated diversification of economy and its' effect on economic growth in Karim Lamido Local Government Area in Taraba State, Nigeria. The study was a descriptive survey research. Target population of the study was 817 participants. Sample of the study was 268 respondents. The sample size was determined using solvins' model for sample size determination. Instrument for data collection was the researchers' developed questionnaire and interview schedule which was used to ask the respondents closed and open ended questions on the study. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The hypotheses formulated were tested at 0.05 level of significance using regression analysis and the associated ANOVA. Findings of the study revealed that there is lag in economic growth, occasioned by lack of economic diversification. The study recommended that people in the study area should intensify effort on diversification of economy in order to realize economic growth for sustainable development.

Keywords: Diversification of economy, Effect, Economic growth.

INTRODUCTION

The most potent and critical factor that impedes or enhance economic growth of any nation is diversification of economy. Diversification of economy is considered imperative because it is believed to be related to increase in financial output. Udeh, Onuoha and Nwokerobia (2021) referred to diversification as creating new avenues for economic growth which involves using the right strategy to boost revenue generated from other sectors of the economy. Economic diversification is highly crucial and fundamental. It pertains to devising several sources of income generation to enhance economic growth. The role of economic diversification is enormous. It is a catalyst for increasing the financial base of a nation. Lack of diversification of economy makes attainment of the expected economic growth a mirage. Attaching importance to diversification of economy in order to enhance economic growth Uzonwanne (2015) elucidated that prior to the discovery of crude oil in 1956, the mainstay of Nigeria economy was agriculture. That the country was primary producer of cash crops such as cocoa, timber, palm-oil, groundnut and rubber which was exported that made the country a major exporter of the crops.

That in the 1960s, and immediately before the oil boom of the 1970s, agriculture contributed 60% to Nigeria's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) 70% to export and 95% to food needs. The implication is that despite the existence and enormous contribution of agricultural sector as a viable source of revenue for the nation, with the advent of oil boom in the 1970s, the sector has been noticeably neglected for heavy dependence on oil revenue. The need to intensify diversification of economy remains. The need assumes that without diversification of economy, many nations will not achieve economic growth.

Greater contribution to economic growth and more wealth increase is realized through diversification of economy. Anyaechie and Areji (2015) described diversification of economy as the process of expanding the range of economic activities both in the production and distribution of goods and services, the widening of the economy to create opportunities for diverse economic activities to create broad-based economy. Derivable from the definition, economic diversification means involvement in several economic activities rather than depending on a single source of income generation. It is an effort toward increasing revenue source for more economic growth. Heavy reliance on a source of income is highly detrimental to economic growth and development. Therefore, there is need for economic diversification. The essence of economic diversification is to provide a strong buffer against the vagaries of economic fluctuation, generate income through investment in a variety of assets for economic growth and sustainable development. Besides, it is geared toward meeting the basic needs of the poor in terms of food, shelter, job creation, clothing, health and to open diverse avenues for economic activity that can accommodate a broad spectrum of people (Udeh, et al, 2021).

The major cause of decline in economic growth of any nation is lack of economic diversification. For instance, there is progressive deterioration of economic growth in Karim Lamido Local Government area. Several factors contribute to this, paramount among which is lack of diversification of economy. Ohunye, et al (2020) while comparing economic growth of a nation from another occasioned by diversification of economy stated that Malaysia is currently ranked the largest producer and exporter of palm oil in the world in spite of the availability of the oil well. The assumption is that diversification of economy is germane in causing economic growth and development of a nation. Given the portentous analogy, it is glaring that heavy reliance on a single source of income extremely militate against economic growth. Supporting diversification of economy in order to facilitate economic growth, Eluogu (2017) wrote that with the recent vagaries in prices of commodities and consequent hardship engendered by over reliance in a single source of revenue, it has become more compelling to Nigerian policy-makers and all stakeholders that diversifying the economy is not optional but mandatory. The veracity of this is that economic growth of any nation becomes achievable when there is diversification of economy.

The many issues that bedevil relative economic growth and stability of any nation or region is lack of diversification of economy. Diversification of economy leads to a more robust and resilient economy. Emphasizing on the need for diversification of economy in order to increase the wealth of a nation, Ugulini, (2019) explained that since production is the hub of economic activities, diversification of economy is imperative not only because it enhances economic growth, but also that it paves way for attainment of sustainable economic development. The basic assumption is that diversification of economy has significant impact on the growth and development of any nation. The role of economic diversification on economic growth is enormous. It is a catalyst and also the cornerstone for optimizing resources to meet the needs of people. Therefore, it is imperative and indeed germane that diversification of economy should be intensified in order to achieve economic growth and sustainable development.

Statement of the Problem

The struggle and general expectation of every nation of the world is high economic growth. This is because it is increase in economic activities that makes a country stable. Where economic growth becomes unachievable, the assumption is that the said nation is not involved in diversification of economy. This is because diversification of economy offers multifarious benefits. It is believable that most nations of the world that are extremely rich and economically stable are engaged in diverse sources of income. This means diversification of economy is a catalyst in enhancing economic growth.

In Karim Lamido, a place highly blessed with available land, it is disheartening that there is market concentration on a source of income. There is abysmal failure as regards diversification of economy. The problem of the study therefore is, what are the effect of diversification of economy on economic growth in the Local Government Area.

Objectives of the Study

The major objective of the study was to investigate effect of diversification of economy on economic growth in Karim Lamido Local Government Area, Taraba State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study intends to;

- 1 Investigate effect of diversification of economy on economic growth
- 2 Find out effort of the people toward diversification of economy
- 3 Determine the relationship between diversification of economy and economic growth of the area.
- 4 Identify the predominant techniques employed by the people for economic growth.

Research questions

The following research questions guided the study

- 1 What is the effect of diversification of economy on economic growth?
- 2 What is the effort of the people toward diversification of economy?
- 3 What is the relationship between diversification of economy and economic growth of the area?
- 4 What are the predominant techniques employed by the people for economic growth?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance

H0₁: There is no significant relationship between diversification of economy and economic growth.

H0₂: There is no significant relationship between diversification of economy and its' effect on economic growth.

Significance of the Study

Findings of the study could be beneficial to government because it will inform them adequately on the need to encourage diversification of economy to boost economic growth. Policy makers could gain from the result of the study because it will make them formulate appropriate policy that will make diversification of economy mandatory in order to maximize economic growth. Top government functionaries could benefit from findings of the study because it will enable them to exercise effort toward diversification of economy for a robust economy. Individuals could gain from the outcome of the study because as the nations' economy is diversified, it will boost economic growth that could lead to employment generation. Findings of the study could be gainful to the general populace because as effort is made to diversify economy, there will be improvement in economic activities to reduction of poverty. Researchers could benefit from the study because it will enable them carryout further research in related areas to facilitate economic growth.

Scope of the Study

The study is delimited to Karim Lamido Local Government area of Taraba State, Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The construct "economic diversification" is the process of devising several sources of revenue generation. This is because the major cause of setback in economic growth is heavy reliance on a source of revenue. The assumption of economic diversification is that there should be increase in sources of income for economic growth and development.

Theoretical Framework

The concern of diversification of economy theory is shift from a single source of income generation to more sources of revenue. According to the theory, diversification of economy raises income generation and increases economic growth. The theory suggests that diversification or increase in the range of business improves the business transaction and yields more dividend. The theory believed that diversification of economy is a strong means of enhancing business. The theorist compared interest on a single source of business and those of several sources and concludes that several sources of business

ranks the best. The theory believed that there is no one best way of increasing and improving economic activities in an organization except through diversification of economy. The theory posits that economic growth must focus on several sources of revenue, since it is the revenue source that facilitate business performance, not market concentration on a source. The theorist criticized those who have heavy reliance on a single source of income and places onus on diversification of economy. The central idea in the theory is its emphasis on diverse sources of income in order to achieve economic growth. The theory is relevant to this study because of its major thrust on diversification of economy as one of the determinant of economic growth. It has conscientized individuals and organizational stakeholders who heavily rely on a single source of revenue and encouraged them to see the need to diversify income source for more gains. The theory is indeed relevant to this study because it has provided useful hints and lays emphasis on the fact that diverse sources of revenue is a catalyst for economic growth.

Empirical Studies

Bakare, (2013) carried out a survey research on the relationship between sustainable agriculture and rural development in Nigeria. Findings of the study showed that the past values of agricultural output could be used to predict the future behaviour of rural development in Nigeria. It was suggested that there is need for policy makers to promote agriculture to a sustainable level by driving rural development. Philip, Fasina and Ogbuagu (2019) conducted a correlational survey research on export diversification and economic growth in Nigeria. Findings of the study revealed that export diversification has a positive but insignificant influence on economic growth in Nigeria because the oil sector still dominates the Nigerian economy while the diversification drive of the government has not been significant in other sectors of the economy. The study recommended that there is need for conscious economic policies that would promote diversification of the entire non-oil sector of the economy. It was concluded that export diversification is an insignificant determinant of economic growth in Nigeria. Ohunyeye, Obamen, Omonona and Agbaeze (2020) conducted a descriptive survey research on effect of economic and agricultural diversification on the economic growth in Nigeria. Findings revealed that government agricultural expenditure does not have a significant effect on gross domestic product. It was suggested that government at all level should increase their budgetary allocations for agriculture and also develop a functional agricultural long term blue print to improve the sector. Miftahu and Abdullahi (2023) conducted a descriptive survey study to examine effect of economic diversification on agricultural output in Taraba State, Nigeria. Findings of the study revealed that diversification has a positive relationship with economic growth in Taraba State. Findings also showed that in order to encourage diversification on agricultural output, there should be increase in government expenditure, policy formulation, increase in soft loans to farmers, subsidies and incentives. Findings further revealed that agricultural diversification ensures food security and increase in agricultural output. It was recommended that agricultural value chain system should be strengthened through increase in government spending and investments encouraged in agricultural production. That agricultural research institutes should be strengthened through provision of research funds, expert skilled and well trained personnel or researchers.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study adopted descriptive survey research design using questionnaire and interview as instruments for data collection. Three research experts validated the instruments. Target population of the study was 817 indigenes of the study area. Sample of the study was 268 respondents. The sample size was determined using Slovinc's model for sample size determination. Procedure for data collection was direct delivery of the questionnaire to the respondents by the researcher and research assistants. Interviews were basically conducted by the researcher on individuals randomly selected based on their in-depth knowledge of the issue being studied. Data collected were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Specifically, the research questions were answered using item by item percentage statistical analysis. Data collected from interview were transcribed and analyzed qualitatively. The null hypotheses formulated were tested at 0.05 level of significance using regression analysis and the associated ANOVA.

RESULTS

The data collected were presented and analyzed as follows:

Research question 1: *What is the effect of diversification of economy on economic growth?*

Table 1:

S/N0	Item Statements	SA%	A%	D%	SD%	Remarks
1	Diversification improves the growth of economy	130 (48.5%)	80 (29.9%)	28 (10.4%)	30 (11.2%)	SA
2	It retards the growth of economy	60 (22.4%)	40 (15%)	28 (10.4%)	140 (52.2%)	SD
3	Diversification makes economy more robust	138 (51.5%)	90 (33.6%)	19 (33.6%)	21 (7.8%)	SA
4	Diversification brings economy of a nation to the expected standard	150 (56%)	75 (28%)	25 (9.3%)	25 (9.3%)	SA
5	It facilitates speedy growth of a nation's economy	128 (47.8%)	90 (33.6%)	25 (33.6%)	25 (9.3%)	SA
6	Diversification makes positive contribution in revenue generation	132 (49.3%)	86 (32.1%)	20 (7.4%)	30 (11.2%)	SA

It is glaring and indeed apparent according to the responses of respondents recorded on the table above that diversification of economy has positive effect on economic growth. This is because it makes economy more robust, facilitates speedy growth of a nation's economy and contributes immensely in revenue generation. The greater percentage of strongly agree recorded on the table above is a clear evidence that diversification of economy is a catalyst in enhancing economic growth of a nation.

Research question 2: *What is the effort of the people toward diversification of economy?*

Table 2:

S/N0	Item Statements	SA%	A%	D%	SD%	Remarks
7	The people are extremely apathetic in their effort toward diversification of economy	150 (56%)	70 (26.1%)	20 (7.5%)	28 (10.4%)	SA
8	The people have diverse sources of income generation	34 (12.7%)	42 (15.7)	82 (30.6%)	110 (41%)	SD
9	The people are highly adamant and tenacious in a source of revenue generation	148 (55.2%)	60 (22.4%)	30 (11.2%)	30 (11.2%)	SA
10	There is a very large farmstead and lands in the area as alternative source of income generation	50 (18.7%)	38 (14.2%)	40 (14.9%)	140 (52.2%)	SD
11	The people are reluctant in devising several sources of revenue generation	152 (56.7%)	66 (24.6%)	20 (7.5%)	30 (11.2%)	SA

Diversification of economy is a critical exercise that requires determination in order to achieve it. The responses of respondents recorded on the table above revealed that in the study area, there is a palpable neglect of diversification of economy. The responses indicates that aside from being adamant and tenacious in a single source of revenue generation, also the people are apathetic and reluctant in devising multiple sources of income generation consequent upon apparent setback in economic growth.

Research question 3: *What is the relationship between diversification of economy and economic growth of the area?*

S/N0	Item Statements	SA%	A%	D%	SD%	Remarks
12	Diversification of economy facilitates economic growth of the area	138 (51.5%)	60 (22.4%)	30 (11.2%)	40 (14.9%)	SA
13	Diversification of economy decreases the rate of economic growth in the area	40 (14.9%)	38 (14.2%)	70 (26.1%)	120 (44.8%)	SD
14	Diversification creates multiple sources of revenue that could improve economic growth	146 (54.5%)	62 (23.1%)	30 (11.2%)	340 (11.2%)	SA
15	Diversification of economy paves way for robust economic growth of the area	148 (55.2%)	60 (22.4%)	29 (10.8%)	31 (11.6%)	SA
16	Diversification of economy prepared the area for more economic activities that could lead to sustainable development	162 (60.5%)	58 (21.6%)	28 (10.4%)	20 (7.5%)	SA

There is a clear indication according to the responses of respondents recorded on the table above that there is a significant positive relationship between diversification of economy and economic growth of the area. This is indicated by the greater percentage of Strongly Agree. The assumption of the respondents is that for economic growth to take place as expected, the role of diversification of economy is salient.

Research question 4: *What are the predominant techniques employed by the people for economic growth?*

Table 4

S/N0	Item Statements	SA%	A%	D%	SD%	Remarks
17	The people are not concerned about employing techniques that could bring about economic growth	148 (55.2%)	70 (26.1%)	30 (11.2%)	20 (7.5%)	SA
18	Most of the people are engaged in fishing as a technique to enhance economic growth	130 (48.5%)	88 (32.8%)	28 (10.5%)	22 (8.2%)	SA
19	The effort at diversification of economy is below expectation	128 (47.8%)	80 (29.8%)	30 (11.2%)	30 (11.2%)	SA
20	The technique employ by the people to boost economic growth is establishment of several business centres	60 (22.4%)	50 (18.7%)	70 (26.1)	88 (32.8%)	SD
21	The people are not committed to employing any technique that could enhance economic growth	120 (44.8%)	80 (29.8%)	38 (14.2%)	30 (11.2%)	SA
22	The people are apathetic in diversifying economy	150 (56%)	70 (26.1%)	28 (10.4%)	20 (7.5%)	SA

The incontrovertible fact according to the responses of respondents recorded on the table above is that the people have blantly refuse to employ techniques that could enhance economic growth. The greater percentage of strongly Agree is an indication that the people heavily rely on a source of income instead of diversification of economy to increase income sources.

Hypotheses Testing

H01: There is no significant relationship between diversification of economy and economic growth.

Table 5: Analysis of variance of regression on relationship between diversification of economy and economic growth.

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean square	F	Sig
Regression	428.265	5	85.653	2.592	.002
Residual	649.824	264	2.461		
Total	1078.089	269			

The F-value of 2.592 which was significant at .002 is a conspicuous indication that diversification of economy is significantly related to economic growth. Therefore, the null hypotheses of no significant linear relationship was rejected at $p < 0.05$.

H02: There is no significant relationship between diversification of economy and its' effect on economic growth.

Table 6: Analysis of variance of regression on relationship between diversification of economy and its' effect on economic growth.

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean square	F	Sig
Regression	341.762	5	68.352	2.328	.023
Residual	688.597	284	2.608		
Total	1030.359	289			

There is a glaring evidence according to the F-value of 2.328 which was significant at .023 that significant relationship abounds between diversification of economy and its' effect on economic growth. Therefore, the null hypotheses of no significant linear relationship was rejected at $p < 0.05$.

DISCUSSION

It is glaring and indeed crystal clear according to findings of the study that there is apparent lack of diversification of economy in the study area which led to setback in economic growth. The assumption of the finding is that there is heavy reliance on a source of revenue generation in the area. The result of the study is in consonance with the proposition of Lioudis (2019) that several zones and regions have fail to diversify economy which led to setback in economic growth. The finding is also in agreement with Ojefia (2016) who encouraged diversification of economy in order to enhance economic growth. Findings of the study is in consensus with Obinna (2016) who lamented that despite the prospect of economic diversification, it is not being taken seriously, and that led to setback in economic growth. Result of the study is in conformity with that of Egboka (2013) that the major cause of decline in economic growth is lack of diversification of economy.

CONCLUSION

Results from findings of the study established that diversification of economy is not a dominant practice in the study area. There is heavy reliance on a source of income. The need to diversify economy to boost economic growth remains.

RECOMMENDATION

The following recommendations are critical

- Government should intensify effort on diversification of economy in order to boost economic growth.
- Individuals and cooperate organizations should encourage diversification of economy so as to realize the intended economic growth

- Stakeholders and relevant agencies should employ diversification of economy in order to achieve economic growth for sustainable development.

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